

Synthesis of dl-DOPA functionalized chelating resin : Its application in separation of metal ions from environmental samples

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Abstract : Chloromethylated polystyrene-divinylbenzene has been functionalized with 3-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl) dl-alanine (dl-DOPA). The resulting chelating resin has been characterized by its elemental analyses, infrared spectroscopy, thermogravimetric analysis and metal ion sorption capacities. It has been used for the preconcentration and separation of Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} and their determination by FAAS. Parameters such as the amount of resin, effect of pH, equilibration rate, sorption and desorption of metal ions and effect of diverse ions have been studied. The sorption capacities increase with increase in pH. Recoveries of the metal ions were 96 ± 5, 97 ± 6, 96 ± 5, 95 ± 8 and 96 ± 5 at 95% confidence level whereas the limits of detection (LOD) are 4.0, 5.0, 0.5, 1.3 and 25.0 mg L⁻¹ for Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} respectively. The calibration curves were linear up to 8 mg L⁻¹ (R² = 0.998), 10 mg L⁻¹ (R² = 1.000), 2 mg L⁻¹ (R² = 0.998), 2 mg L⁻¹ (R² = 1.000) and 5 mg L⁻¹ (R² = 0.979) for Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} respectively. The reliability of the environment friendly method has been tested by analyzing certified samples.

Keywords : 3-(3,4-Dihydroxyphenyl) dl-alanine (dl-DOPA), chelating resin, solid phase extraction, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Pb^{II}.

Introduction

In the last twenty years the use of chelating resins has increased extensively¹. Extraction of metal ions using chelating resins has several advantages over conventional methods. The basic advantages in this case are increased selectivity, high preconcentration factor and easy handling. The use of instrumental methods for trace metal quantification frequently requires preconcentration procedures to lower the detection limits. Chelating resins are capable of preconcentrating metal ions selectively and may be easily coupled with flame atomic absorption spectrometric (FAAS) determination to enhance its sensitivity. Chelating resin method can be said to be an eco-friendly one since it uses only a small amount of reusable functionalized resin and eluting aqueous solvent, which in turn also, increases the sensitivity of the system.

The sorption characteristics of the metal ions generally depend upon the size of the chelate ring and metal ion, number of donor atoms/binding site of the functional group, type of donor atoms (hard or soft)², oxidation state of the metal ion, pH of the system etc. Generally, chelating ligands bound to copolymers by covalent bonds are much more resistant to external effects

compared to those immobilized by simple impregnation. In the literature, many chelating resins such as Cibacron Blue F3GA³, quinalizarin⁴, *o*-aminobenzoic acid⁵, thiosalicylic acid⁶, 2,3-dihydropyridine⁷, polystyrene supported diethanol amine⁸, ammonium pyrrolidine dithiocarbamate⁹, piperidine dithiocarbamate¹⁰, tiron¹¹, pyrogallol¹² are described having chloromethylated polystyrene divinylbenzene (PS-DVB), Amberlite XAD-n (polystyrene divinylbenzene) etc., as the polymeric backbone, which were used for preconcentration and separation of metal ions.

The determination of trace amounts of zinc, cobalt and nickel is important in metallurgy and environmental analytical chemistry. There is a growing need for procedures with high sensitivity and selectivity for the determination of these cations because they have important roles in biological science and industry¹³. In addition these elements are usually present together in real samples¹⁴. Therefore, it is important to measure them in the presence of each other. Several reports have been published on the simultaneous determination of zinc, cobalt and nickel by FAAS^{15,16}.

It is known that l-DOPA is used in the treatment of Parkinson's disease and can coordinate as a bidentate

Scheme 1. Synthesis of dl-DOPA functionalized resin.

ligand through either the catecholate (O,O) or the amino acid (O,N) end of the molecule. Furthermore, it is known that transition metal ions having biological roles interact with catecholamines. It is reported that pH is a sensitive determinant of the binding mode of Cu-DOPA¹⁷. At pH 5 a blue-purple coloured square planar complex of Cu-DOPA can be isolated and the bonding mode is purely via amine carboxylate linkage. Above pH 7 the linkage is completely an O,O linkage. Again, catecholato Fe^{III} complexes are widely distributed in biological systems. It is seen that Fe^{III} complexes of DOPA are stable at biological pH i.e. pH 7¹⁸.

The aim of this work was to synthesize 3-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl) dl-alanine (dl-DOPA) functionalized chloromethylated polystyrene divinyl benzene chelating resin where the chelating ligand is bound to the copolymer via a covalent linkage and to use the product as sorbent for separation and preconcentration of heavy metals like Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} from their aqueous solution.

Fig. 1. Exchange capacities of bivalent metal ions at different pH.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization of the resin :

The resin was synthesized through the steps shown in Scheme 1. The nitrogen content of the resin was found to be 2.79% indicating 1.99 mmol g⁻¹ of the final resin. Chloromethylated resin contained 4 mmol g⁻¹ of chlorine. Based on nitrogen content, conversion efficiency from chloromethylated resin to the final resin is 38%. The IR spectra of the final resin were compared with those of the chloromethylated resin and chelating ligand. It was noted that FTIR spectra of polymers are complicated. Therefore, only a few peaks could be assigned with reasonable certainty. The band at 676 cm⁻¹ for -C-Cl stretching had disappeared in the final resin. A few new bands appeared, e.g. those at 3422 cm⁻¹ along with bands at 1641 cm⁻¹ showed the presence of free -NH₂ groups in the resin. The bands at 1438 cm⁻¹ and 1264 cm⁻¹ could be due to phenolic -OH stretching and 1697 cm⁻¹ could be due to C=O stretching. Other vibrations are due to dl-DOPA moiety are 1795 cm⁻¹, 1901 cm⁻¹ and 2220 cm⁻¹ are due to dl-DOPA. There was a possibility of N-alkylation. However carboxylate in DMF was more nucleophilic compared to nitrogen, hence O-alkylation is believed to occur to a greater extent.

The chemical stability of the resin was checked by keeping it mixed with 1–12 M each of HNO₃, HCl and NaOH for 7 days. No significant change in nitrogen content was observed in treated resin. Thus, the resin is stable in acid, and alkali. Thermogravimetric analysis showed that the resin is stable up to 310 °C. However, a 5% mass loss up to 120 °C may be due to sorbed water. From the retention and elution cycle it is found that the resin can be reused, with the same exchange capacity, even after 30 times of regeneration resulted in no loss of ligating efficacy. The time required for 50% uptake for Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} was found to be 12, 10, 12, 14 and 18 min respectively. The resin was suitable for column operation under a low flow rate typically 0.1–0.5 ml min⁻¹.

Sorption and desorption of metal ions :

The sorption capacities of Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} on dl-DOPA resin as a function of pH were determined by batch method and the results are shown in Fig. 1. The maximum capacities for Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} are 0.03, 0.031, 0.056, 0.048 and 0.104 mmol g⁻¹ respectively at pH range 4.5–6.0. The low

Table 1. Desorption of Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} by different eluents

Eluents	Recovery (%)				
	Ni ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	Pb ^{II}
0.01 M HCl	38.7	41.5	56.8	28.6	32.4
0.1 M HCl	48.6	67.5	74.6	45.5	55.5
1 M HCl	75.8	85.8	87.5	72.4	87.6
2 M HCl	95.6	97.5	100.8	87.5	95.8
0.01 M HNO ₃	35.2	50.1	45.5	32.5	21.8
0.1 M HNO ₃	45.6	65.4	62.1	45.3	35.5
1 M HNO ₃	78.5	88.5	76.4	88.6	78.3
2 M HNO ₃	97.4	97.5	90.5	98.7	99.6
1 M SSA	101.5	-	-	-	-
1 M NaOAc	-	-	-	-	100.8
1 M NaF	-	-	100.0	-	-
1 M NaI	-	-	-	102.7	-

exchange capacity was perhaps due to the rigidity of the polymeric matrix, inability of all the chelating groups to participate in chelation for steric restriction and large size of the ions being analysed.

The basicity of nitrogen decreases due to protonation at lower pH and hence cannot bind M(II). With increase in pH, the tendency of protonation decreases and it can bind metal ions through the lone pair of nitrogen followed by chelation via basic oxygen atoms. The effect of different eluents on the desorption of the five metal ions are given in Table 1.

1 M sulphosalicylic acid, 1 M sodium acetate, 1 M sodium fluoride and 1 M sodium iodide were found to be the selective eluting agents for Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} respectively. Co^{II} could be eluted out with 2 M HNO₃ or 2 M HCl.

Effect of diverse ions :

The effects of diverse ions on the sorption of the five metal ions were examined by batch equilibration experiments and the results are presented in Table 2. The presence of diverse metal ions like alkali, alkaline earth and first transition series including mercury and silver did not interfere in the sorption step which suggests the applicability of the resin for trace preconcentration of target metal ions from complex matrix.

Though Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} are known to form complex with DOPA, and the complexation occurs at biological pH i.e. pH 7 or in the alkaline pH region¹⁹. Cu^{II} is known to form a square planar O,N complex with DOPA at pH 5¹⁷. In the present study, the O atom being bonded to C of the polymeric structure, possibly poses steric hindrance

Table 2. Separation of 2 µg ml⁻¹ each of Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} in presence of foreign ions

Foreign ion ^a	Recovery ^b (%)				
	Ni ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	Pb ^{II}
Hg ^{II}	95.1 ± 1.3	94.3 ± 0.9	98.1 ± 0.5	95.4 ± 0.5	96.3 ± 0.7
Ag ^I	97.3 ± 0.7	97.5 ± 0.5	94.5 ± 1.2	91.5 ± 0.5	94.1 ± 0.7
Cu ^{II}	96.1 ± 0.6	95.1 ± 0.4	95.5 ± 0.3	92.2 ± 0.3	95.3 ± 0.5
Fe ^{III}	98.5 ± 0.2	97.4 ± 0.4	97.3 ± 0.9	98.3 ± 0.7	97.3 ± 0.3
Mn ^{II}	98.2 ± 0.3	97.2 ± 0.7	99.1 ± 0.7	97.1 ± 0.9	97.1 ± 0.9
Na ^I	100.1 ± 0.5	98.1 ± 0.2	99.1 ± 0.5	97.5 ± 0.8	99.1 ± 0.2
Ca ^{II}	98.4 ± 0.6	98.3 ± 0.5	99.4 ± 0.3	96.1 ± 0.6	98.2 ± 0.1
Ba ^{II}	99.1 ± 0.5	98.3 ± 0.5	100.1 ± 0.3	95.4 ± 0.5	99.4 ± 0.4

^aEach foreign ion added, 2000 µg and Hg^{II} 2000 ng.

^bThe results are average of five determinations.

Table 3. Determination of Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} in certified samples

Metal ion	Standard reference materials and metal ion values (µg g ⁻¹)								
	Citrus leaves			Chlorella			Pond sediment		
	Certified	Values ^a	Error (%)	Certified	Values ^a	Error (%)	Certified	Values ^a	Error (%)
Ni ^{II}	0.6 ± 0.3	0.63 ± 0.4	+5.0	–	–	–	40 ± 3	42.50 ± 3.50	+6.3
Co ^{II}	–	–	–	0.87 ± 0.05	0.77 ± 0.08	-11.5	27 ± 3	29.25 ± 2.50	+7.4
Zn ^{II}	29 ± 2	29.65 ± 2.41	+2.2	20.50	21.50 ± 3.55	+4.8	343 ± 17	348.50 ± 17.50	+1.6
Cd ^{II}	0.03 ± 0.01	0.029 ± 0.07	-3.3	260 ± 0.14	275.45 ± 0.25	+5.9	0.82 ± 0.06	0.78 ± 0.09	-4.8
Pb ^{II}	13.3 ± 2.4	13.8 ± 2.5	+3.8	0.60	0.65 ± 0.15	+8.3	105 ± 6	110.25 ± 7.50	+5.0

^aThe results are average of five determinations.

resulting in the unavailability of (O,N) donor sites. Hence no uptake of Cu^{II} was observed in 1–6 pH range. Thus, Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} did not interfere in the uptake of Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} ions.

Analytical figures of merit :

The calibration curves for determination of Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} were found to be linear up to 8 mg L⁻¹ (R² = 0.998), 10 mg L⁻¹ (R² = 1.000), 2 mg L⁻¹ (R² = 0.998), 2 mg L⁻¹ (R² = 1.000) and 5 mg L⁻¹ (R² = 0.979) respectively. The detection limit were calculated as the concentration corresponding to a 3σ value of the blank signal and were found to be 4.0, 5.0, 0.5, 1.3 and 25.0 µg L⁻¹ for Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} respectively. The precision of the method was evaluated by five successive elution and retention cycles with 0.1 g of bivalent metal

ions in 100 ml of solution. It was observed that the percent recoveries were more than 96 ± 5, 97 ± 6, 96 ± 5, 95 ± 8 and 96 ± 5 at 95 % confidence level for Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} respectively. The preconcentration factors for the metal ions in the same order were found to be 150, 100, 150, 50 and 50, respectively.

Determination of the metals in different certified samples :

Various certified biological samples were digested in the environmentally friendly way using a microwave oven. Then each metal ion viz. Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} was analyzed after separation through dl-DOPA resin and the results are shown in Table 3.

The results showed that the resin containing dl-DOPA is very selective for Pb^{II} at pH 6.0. Compared to the solid

Table 4. A comparative study of dl-DOPA resin with some other resins

Functional group	Exchange capacity (mmol g ⁻¹)					Reference
	Ni ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	Pb ^{II}	
dl-DOPA	0.030	0.031	0.056	0.048	0.104	Present work
Cibacron Blue F3GA	–	–	0.103	0.096	0.080	3
Quinalizarin	–	0.027	0.021	0.015	0.025	4
o-Aminobenzoic acid	0.121	0.091	0.116	0.080	0.059	5
Thiosalicylic acid	0.309	0.106	0.047	0.197	–	6
2,3-Dihydroxypyridine	0.220	0.087	0.176	0.150	0.065	7
Polystyrene supported diethanol amine	–	–	–	0.036	0.066	8
Ammonium pyrrolidine dithiocarbamate	0.127	–	0.155	0.082	0.047	9
Piperidine dithiocarbamate	0.122	–	0.160	0.084	0.049	10
Tiron	0.215	0.110	0.169	0.084	0.060	11
Pyrogallol	0.069	0.069	0.069	0.046	0.032	12

phase exchangers as shown in Table 4 this resin showed the best exchange capacity for lead. This selectivity may be due to the availability of a pair of electrons on basic nitrogen and oxygen donor atoms. Thus the resin can be very effective in separation of lead from mineralised environmental samples. Nevertheless, the resin has also been successfully used for the separation of Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents :

Atomic absorption spectrometric measurements were carried out with a GBC AVANTA Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (model 908 BT) with lamp current and wavelength set to 10 mA and 232.0 nm for nickel, 10 mA and 240.7 nm for cobalt, 5 mA and 213.7 nm for zinc, 3 mA and 228.8 nm for cadmium and 3 mA and 283.3 nm for lead. Systronics digital pH meter (model 335) was used for pH adjustments. A domestic Samsung microwave oven (model CE2933) with a 2450 MHz frequency magnetron and 900 W maximum power and a polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) reactor having 115 ml internal volume, 1 cm cell wall thickness and hermetic screw caps were used for digestion.

Chloromethylated polystyrene resin was obtained from Fluka and dl-DOPA from LOBA, India. Standards of metal ions used were procured from E. Merck (Germany). Working solutions were prepared by appropriate dilution of stock with deionised water. All other chemicals were of reagent grade. The glass apparatus used were soaked in 4 M nitric acid for overnight and cleaned with double distilled water before use. The reference materials analyzed were : *citrus leaves* (1572, SRM, National Bureau of Standards), *chlorella* (NIES, CRM 3) and *pond sediment* (NIES 2) Japan.

Microwave-assisted digestion of certified samples :

Portions of 100 to 150 mg of certified samples were treated in a domestic microwave oven in sequence in a 115 ml hermetically sealed PTFE reactor with 1.5 ml of HF (450 W, 2.5 min), 4 ml of aqua regia (450 W, 2.5 min) and 3 ml of H₂O₂ (450 W, 2.5 min). The digested sample was boiled with 5 ml of saturated boric acid for 10 min in a water bath to remove excess of HF.

Synthesis of the dl-DOPA resin :

Air dried chloromethylated polystyrene copolymer containing 2% divinyl benzene was used as the starting material. The copolymer bead (1 g, 200–400 mesh) was treated with 800 mg 3-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl) dl-alanine (dl-DOPA) in the presence of sodium carbonate (400 mg) in *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) to obtain a dark brown polymer. The resin was washed thoroughly with DMF to remove excess dl-DOPA and then with 1 M HCl to remove excess base. Finally, it was washed with double distilled water, dried and stored at room temperature for further use.

Metal ion capacity as a function of pH :

The metal ion capacity was determined for Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} using batch technique. A measured excess of metal ion solution was added to 50 mg of the dl-DOPA resin taken in a 50 ml conical flask. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 1.0–6.0 with 0.1 M hydrochloric acid or 0.2 M sodium acetate. The metal ions in solution were determined by FAAS using an air-acetylene flame.

Studies of various eluting agents for desorption :

The resin obtained by above treatment was shaken with 30 ml of various eluants viz. 0.01–2 M HCl and HNO₃, 1 M SSA (sulfosalicylic acid) and 1 M NaOAc (sodium acetate), 1 M NaF (sodium fluoride) and 1 M NaI (sodium iodide) for 24 h and filtered. The concentration of the metal ion was determined in the filtrate as above.

Column operation :

Air dried resin (1.5 g) was immersed in double distilled water and allowed to swell for 24 h. A 130 mm × 10 mm glass column was packed with swollen beads to a bed volume of 2 ml. The sorption and desorption characteristics for the metal ion in the column was studied at the flow rate of 0.5 ml min⁻¹. Sorbed Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} were eluted completely either with 0.01–2 M HCl/HNO₃, 1 M SSA or 1 M NaOAc.

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